

The soil is fine loam overlying silty loam and deep gravel. Vegetation is predominantly *Imperata cylindrica* with *Ophiuros* spp. and *Digitaria* spp. Annual rainfall averages 1,400 mm.

We dibbled 5-6 seeds/hill at 20- × 20-cm spacing, keeping sowing depth uniform. Each genotype was planted on 15 m². The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design with five replications. We recorded yield data for 100 hills (4 m² net area)/genotype per replication and yield components for 20 hills/genotype per replication. Data from only three of the replications showed consistency and were used for analysis of variance.

Tambu, Wantok, Niupela, NG8313, and NG8315 significantly outyielded the other genotypes (see table). They also

Yield and yield components of rice varieties under upland field condition in Gaidusden, Markham Valley, Morobe Province, PNG, 1991.^a

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Panicle fertility (%)	Harvest index (%)	1000-grain wt (g)
Tambu	2.4 a	70.3 a	20.4 a	21.8 a	44.1 e	39.5 b	0.5 e	16.0 c
Wantok	2.3 a	70.6 b	19.7 a	21.0 a	42.7 c	41.3 b	0.4 e	17.2 c
Niupela	2.7 a	112.5 a	11.5 c	22.5 a	73.7 a	50.9 a	0.5 e	13.7 d
Senis	1.2 b	74.6 b	12.6 b	21.4 a	26.8 d	23.5 d	0.6 d	15.9 c
BR12-5-5-1-1	0.6 c	71.7 b	16.6 b	21.2 a	38.6 c	46.9 a	0.4 e	14.2 d
NG8297	1.1 b	74.2 b	15.5 b	21.2 a	32.1 d	31.5 c	0.7 c	17.2 c
NG8304	1.2 b	73.1 b	14.2 b	20.1 a	28.1 d	29.0 c	0.9 c	19.1 b
NG8313	2.7 a	82.1 b	24.0 a	20.1 a	58.1 b	49.5 a	1.7 a	16.5 c
NG8315	2.4 a	58.1 c	19.3 a	20.1 a	21.2 e	22.4 d	1.8 a	24.7 a
NG8321	1.5 b	58.2 c	11.0 c	20.7 a	31.5 d	39.7 b	1.2 b	19.4 b
CV (%)	14.5							

^a In a column, figures followed by different letters significantly differ at the 5% level by DMRT.

outperformed the others in yield components, such as productive tillers/hill, filled grains/panicle, harvest index, and 1,000-grain weight.

These genotypes will be tested in different agroecological zones before they are recommended for general cultivation in the country. □

Pest resistance—diseases

Reaction of rice genotypes of different origins and genealogy to blast (B1) disease in Nigeria

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Rice B1 *Pyricularia grisea* is a major constraint to rice production in Africa. Its severity is greatest in the uplands, rainfed lowlands, and inland valleys of West Africa and in the cold-prone mid-altitude areas in the East, Central, and Southern Africa sub-region.

We screened 1,253 lines and best local check varieties for reaction to B1 at an upland site at IITA, (7° N, 3° E, and 200 m above sea level) with reliably high B1 levels. The lines were entries in various INGER-Africa nurseries in 1991 and in the International Rice Blast Nursery (IRBN). The B1 screening plot was laid out to conform with the IRBN plot design.

Analysis of *Standard evaluation system for rice* B1 score data revealed that of the 266 entries in the upland nurseries,

Adapted upland rice varieties common in the ancestry of B1-resistant lines.^a

Variety	Origin	Lines developed (no.)
<i>Adapted varieties or progenitor</i>		
Colombia 1	Colombia	32
Dourado Precoce	Brazil	18
Eloni	Surinam	17
Iguape Cateto	Brazil	12
LAC23	Liberia	8
Moroberekan	West Africa	17
OS6	Zaire	7
Palawan	Philippines	14
63-83	Cote d'Ivoire	19
<i>Modern varieties</i>		
IAC25	Brazil	12
IR13149-19-1	IIRI	9
IRAT104	Cote d'Ivoire	21
IRAT112	Cote d'Ivoire	12
IRAT113	Cote d'Ivoire	34
IRAT212	IITA	17
ITA235	IITA	10
M312A	Cote d'Ivoire	32
TOx7	IITA	8
TOx1010	IITA	19
TOx1367-7	IITA	15
TOx1780	IITA	8
Total		341

^a Of 1,253 entries screened, 580 were recorded as B1 resistant. Among these, more than 59% were derived from the adapted varieties listed above.

145 scored 0-1 and only four scored 7-9. Of the 268 entries in the irrigated nurseries, 24 scored 0-1 and 55 scored 7-9. Of the 539 entries in both African and global B1 nurseries, 108 scored 0-1 and 110 scored 7-9.

Most entries in the irrigated and rainfed lowland nurseries had intermediate scores of 4-6 (see figure, a). In the upland nurseries, however, entries with scores of 0-3 had the highest frequency. Similarly, many entries in the

Rice Yellow Mottle Virus (RYMV) Nursery were observed to be B1 resistant. This is because most of the lines developed for RYMV resistance came from adapted upland varieties, such as 63-83, Dourado Precoce, Iguape Cateto, and Moroberekan, which are also B1 resistant.

Cluster analysis of the results by groups of entries from the same origin showed that African and Latin American entries performed at par or better than those from Asia, USA, Europe, and the Middle East with respect to proportion of B1-resistant entries (see figure, b). Of the entries with superior performance, more originated from Africa than from Latin America.

The close similarity in superior performance of improved African and Latin American entries reflects the similarities in the host-pathogen-stress complex. Some traditional varieties have been used more often than others in the parentage of the B1-tolerant lines

Blast scores for 1,253 entries in 1991 INGER-Africa nurseries grouped into major ecosystems or stresses and by region. Scored by *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale 0-9.

originating from different regions (see table). These include varieties 63-83, Colombia 1, Dourado Precoce, Iguape Cateto, and Moroberekan.

The results indicate that adapted genotypes from Africa and Latin America serve as good sources for durable B1 resistance for upland rice in Africa. □

Reaction of some rice cultures to leaf blast (BI), brown spot (BS), and leaf scald (LSc)

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We screened rice cultures Kalinga, CR628-2, CR635-42, Karna, IET7 191, and Intan during the 1988 and 1989 wet seasons in fields with high disease

pressure. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Plot size was 6 × 3 m. We applied fertilizer 60-75-87.5 kg NPK/ha. Total rainfall during crop growth was 644.8 mm in 1988 and 1,389.3 mm in 1989.

All of the entries were moderately to highly susceptible to leaf BI, moderately susceptible to susceptible to BS, and susceptible to LSc (see table). Days to 50% flowering, plant height, and yield for each culture are reported in the table. □

Reaction of rice cultures to leaf BI, BS, and LSc.

Culture	Disease score ^a			Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Yield (t/ha)
	Leaf blast	Brown spot	Leaf scald			
Kalinga	9	7	7	86	67.8	1.1
CR628-2	9	7	7	97	64.5	1.1
CR635-42	9	6	7	97	77.3	1.1
<i>Checks</i>						
Karna	9	7	7	90	62.1	2.0
IET7191	9	5	7	107	67.6	2.4
Intan	7	6	7	117	67.9	2.0
LSD (0.05)						0.1

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Grain quality

Aromatic and quality rice improvement in Tamil Nadu, India

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Consumers in Tamil Nadu prefer rice Varieties with good cooking quality and scent. These rices receive a premium price in the market and have export potential. Many of them are tall indicas that lodge easily and have low yield potential. We evaluated 10 quality rice varieties of medium duration (around 140 d) during the 1990 thaladi season (Sep-Oct to Jan-Feb) to assess their

performance and feasibility of use as donors for aromatic and quality rice improvement in Tamil Nadu.

We transplanted 30-d-old seedlings in 10-m² plots with 20- × 10-cm spacing. We used 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

Milled rice samples were used to assess scent in a cooking test. It was evaluated using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).